

C1b. Sources, distribution, fate and behaviour of plastics and associated chemical in soils

ID 69. Mobility and fate of biodegradable microplastics in agricultural soils

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Biodegradable mulch films have been designed as a sustainable solution to mitigate plastic pollution in agricultural soils. However, environmental concern persists about the fate of microplastics (MPs) produced during the degradation of these films. The release of MPs poses potential risks to crops, soil microorganisms and groundwater quality. This study investigates the mobility and fate of polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) fragments from biodegradable mulch films in soil, focusing on their transport through surface runoff and infiltration as a consequence of rainfall and irrigation considering two scenarios: bare soil and crop cultivation. Six collectors (2x1x0.5 m) were filled with natural soil and PBAT fragments (D_{50} : 160 μm ; load: 0.5 wt%) were added to the upper 4 cm of soil. Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) was cultivated in three of the collectors. Periodic sampling was conducted for 5 months to collect runoff water and infiltrating water (10 cm and 30 cm). After harvesting, soil samples were also collected at various depths for MP analysis. PBAT fragments were identified and quantified using μFTIR . The results indicate that >65% of the MPs remained in the soil. Furthermore, the presence of crop influenced MP transport via runoff, as evidenced by the lower concentrations of MPs in runoff water and higher MP accumulation in the cultivated soils. Additionally, MP infiltration was minimal, with less than 1% of the total MPs detected between 25–30 cm depth